

A SCOPING REVIEW OF THE BENEFITS OF AI ADOPTION IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Historically, South Africa has been a nation plagued by socio economic disparities that has negatively impacted its growth and transformation. However in recent years the nation has sought to embrace the rapid changes brought upon by globalisation; leaving governments and established sectors questioning their relevance and longevity. In order to participate in a digital future, the transformation of governments and its respective sectors are crucial to its success. In South Africa, the Artificial Intelligence (AI) market is experiencing a rapid growth that is driven by the emergence of AI policies, and is projected to reach 0.90bn USD in 2024. The AI market is further expected to grow at an annual rate of 28.22%, resulting in a market volume of 4.00bn USD by the year 2030. A theoretical gap exists in current South African literature with regards to the perceived benefits of AI adoption within the South African construction sector, in resolving infrastructure delivery challenges. An interpretivist philosophy was chosen for the study. This approach allows for a systematic literature review, synthesized via the PRISMA 2020 process; further accompanied by a thematic analysis of qualitative data. NVivo software was utilised as a tool to thematically analyse 222 indexed publications on the role of AI in the construction sector and its perceived benefits, revealing subjective experiences and meanings. Findings illustrate that the integration of AI within the South African construction sector can enhance productivity, efficiency, quality and promote cost reduction. In order for South Africa to exploit the full potential and overarching benefits of AI in the construction sector; the sector and its governing bodies are required to develop a strategic AI framework that carefully considers the social, ethical and economic implications, ensuring that AI benefits are broadly shared, and that the risks are mitigated effectively.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Automation, Benefits, Construction, South Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

The 4th Industrial Revolution (4IR) signified a paradigm shift that globally altered economic, political and social environments. 4IR further introduced innovative technologies which included artificial intelligence, block chain and advanced mobile networks, which has powered a global digital revolution. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a force for transformation and as a critical component of 4IR, in reshaping both social and cultural landscapes; and has promoted the economic growth of nations [1]. It merges the physical and digital worlds, enabling object handling, sensing, communicating, acquiring knowledge, and making logical deductions, enhancing efficiency, and in tackling intricate issues through forecasts and broad conclusions [2]. In 2024, the South African AI market experienced an immense growth, driven by the emergence of AI policies and regulations, with the government aiming to promote AI development while also addressing concerns surrounding data privacy, job displacement and technology bias. The South African AI market is anticipated to grow at an annual rate of

28.22% between 2024 and 2030, resulting in a combined market volume of 72.5 billion ZAR. The potential for growth spans across a variety of sectors, offering opportunities to revolutionize operations, improve productivity, and enhance critical socio-economic service delivery that supports education, healthcare, transportation and legal systems in South Africa [3].

The South African construction sector, responsible for socio economic development and maintenance is essential to the success of the country's economy, contributing an estimated 160.65 billion ZAR to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) in 2024. Global research efforts are being made to enhance the construction sector by transitioning from conventional construction methods to more innovative and appropriate approaches which include artificial intelligence [4]. The sector is viewed as a potential flywheel for economic development and sustainability, with the need for bold initiatives such as AI [5]. AI enhances automation, efficiency, and dependability by bridging the gap between physical and digital realms in the construction sector. Although South Africa is still in its infancy stage of AI development compared to developed nations, there is a growing momentum in the construction sector that is aimed at developing AI for societal and economic benefits while ensuring ethical and regulatory standards are maintained [6] [7].

This study adopts an interpretivist philosophy and seeks to address a knowledge gap existent in South African literature on the perceived benefit of AI in the South African construction sector, through the adoption of a qualitative research framework. A comprehensive systematic literature review, guided by PRIISMA 2020 was conducted using a refined keyword search on Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar databases.

NVivo software offers a thematical analysis of the literature, seeking to ascertain the role of AI across the South African construction sector, in identifying the perceived benefits of AI adoption in South African construction sector and in recommending framework for implementation towards integrating AI in the South African construction sector.

In order to face the inefficiencies, present in the current construction sector, the successful implementation of an artificial intelligence framework should be integrated across all construction sector activities. The research gap strengthens the justification of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Artificial Intelligence

Since the 1940's, researchers have focused on the ability of digital technologies to execute intelligent tasks, with John McCarthy having coined the term artificial intelligence in 1955, which sparked a revolution. John McCarthy imagined an era of time when intelligent technologies imitate human behaviour, going beyond biologically detectable methods to include non-observable ones, setting the stage for the 21st century AI landscape [8][9][10]. Researchers have often debated AI from two differing ideologies; one that focuses on neural thinking and the other that identifies logical rules, to achieve intelligent behaviour. This debate functions on various dimensions, which includes behaviour AI, structure AI, function AI, capability AI, and principle AI [11][12].

AI refers to the ability of self-governing mechanical and electronic devices to perform tasks autonomously through intelligent control. According to the concept, digital technologies have the ability to develop intelligence, learn autonomously, adapt to unique conditions, and self-correct their mistakes, allowing them to think freely without directions and enhance various sectors [1][13].

The concept of AI has expanded into a variety of sectors such as manufacturing, agriculture, finance, healthcare, education, construction, law and information communications and technology [14]. Three categories of AI conceptualizations exist. *Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI)*: Weather forecasting and language translation employ this particular form of AI; *Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)*: AI that has the ability to solve complicated issues on its own using mental models and personality traits and *Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI)*: AI that will surpass human skills in various disciplines if it can ever be constructed [15][16].

The main applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the construction industry are machine learning, automation, robotics, computer vision, knowledge-based systems, automated planning and scheduling, natural language processing, and optimization, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Components, types, and subfield of AI [16]

Investment in AI has grown, with developed and emerging countries both dedicating substantial funding towards AI research, as it enhances a country's economy through budget optimization which assists in stabilizing sectors and enhances the sustainable growth of a nation [17][18]. Authors have identified the leading countries in AI research and technology; with China at 65%, The United States of America and Israel at 50% respectively, Canada at 45% and The United Kingdom at 35% in AI adoption. In 2022, the worldwide AI implementation rate rose from 31% to 35%, with 42% of sectors exploring AI adoption as highlighted in table 1 below. It should be noted that information, communications, technology and software development are leading with a 58% global adoption rate; while the construction sector is lagging behind at 24.5% [19][20][21][22].

Table 1: AI Adoption Rate across Sectors

SECTOR	ADOPTION RATE
Information, Communications, Technology and Software Development	Approximately 58% of companies in the technology sector are integrating AI into their operations. This includes companies developing AI technologies and those using AI for automation and analysis.
Finance and Insurance	Approximately 44% of companies within this sector are utilizing AI for various tasks such as detecting fraud, mitigating risks, automating customer support, and offering personalized financial advice.
Healthcare	Approximately 39% of medical facilities are currently employing artificial intelligence for activities including examining medical images, handling patient information, uncovering new medications, delivering tailored medical treatment, and improving operational effectiveness.
Manufacturing	Approximately 35% of manufacturing companies are leveraging AI for predictive maintenance, quality control, supply chain optimization, and automation of production processes.
Retail and eCommerce	Approximately 31% of retail and eCommerce businesses are using AI for customer service chatbots, personalized marketing recommendations, supply chain management, and inventory optimization.
Construction	As of latest available data, the adoption of AI in the construction industry is 24.5% which is still low compared to some other industries. Estimates suggest that only 8-10% of construction companies are actively using AI technologies.

(Reference: [21][22])

AI embodies the forefront of industrial digitalization and digital revolution across nations and sectors, marking the next evolutionary leap in technological advancement. However, the construction sector is lagging behind due to the traditional nature of the sector, government support, institutional barriers and reforms, policy development, funding, skills scarcity, socio-economic factors, long implementation periods and the availability of digital resources [23].

2.2. Artificial Intelligence and the Construction Sector

The AI Construction Market surpassed 3.20 billion USD in 2023 and is projected to grow from 3.93 billion USD in 2024 to USD 22.68 billion by 2032. The construction sector is an essential part of the economy and has a major impact on driving economic growth and ensuring national sustainability yet is often viewed as highly volatile and unsafe; with construction accidents causing 30-40% of worldwide fatalities [24][25]. Moreover, it is regarded as one of the least advanced sectors in global digital transformation. However, in recent years, the global construction sector has recognized the capability of AI to enhance economic growth through increased productivity, reduced expenses, and promoting innovation. The sector's increase is credited to improved efficiency and productivity by optimizing project scheduling, resource allocation, and project management, quality and safety; which results in decreased timeframes and costs [26] [27][28]. Harnessing the capacity of AI to analyze vast quantities of data enhances the processes of planning, resource allocation, and decision-making within the construction sector [29]. AI increases safety on construction sites by continuously monitoring, identifying potential dangers, and ensuring compliance with regulations. It also provides quality assurance and identification of defects, resulting in enhanced construction quality and decreased rework [30].

Figure 2: Artificial Intelligence in Construction Market Size [25]

The South African AI market is estimated to be worth 3.18-billion USD in 2024 and expected to grow to 8.74-billion USD by 2030, with the South African AI Construction sector anticipated to be a significant contributor. The post-pandemic South African construction industry is now set to grow at 5.8% between 2023-27, outpacing the country's GDP by four times. Governmental investments in large construction projects have been the leading force behind the sectors growth. After a lack of construction projects over the past decade, the sector faced

a mass exodus of skilled labor due to its instability. The Construction Industry Development Board highlights a resurged demand for contractors, subcontractors, and construction industry professionals over the next decade. However, the sector is not without its challenges which include; poor electricity infrastructure; materials cost and shortages; transport and logistic disruptions; climate change; labor shortages; slow technology adoption; project delays; cost overruns and the lack of funding [31][32][33].

In South Africa, AI provides opportunities to overcome the abovementioned challenges associated with infrastructure development and accelerate its progress, which is vital for economic growth. The advent of Construction 4.0 bridges the gap between 4IR and the construction sector, with AI technologies offering a significant opportunity to boost productivity on construction projects, which are often plagued by infrastructure backlogs, industry fragmentation and socio-economic discourse; by simplifying procedures, through enhanced efficiency, problem-solving, decision-making, and collaborative learning practices throughout the project lifecycle.

Figure 3: Types, Components and Sub-fields of Artificial Intelligence in the South African Construction Industry [27]

The incorporation of digital technologies such as, Machine Learning, Knowledge-Based Systems, Robotics, Natural Language Processing, Automated Planning and Scheduling and Optimization into construction practices can assist the industry in becoming among the top productive sectors, nationally and globally [27] [34] [35][36].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An interpretivist philosophy was used to develop a qualitative framework for systematically analyzing the benefits of AI adoption in the South African construction industry. Systematic literature reviews are reliant on a seven-step process; i.e. database selection, keyword selection, keyword search, data extraction, screening, bibliometric analysis and the analysis of results.

NVivo Software tool was used to thematically analyze and recognize the recurring themes present in the data with respect to the manner in which AI can positively affect the South African construction industry.

The research framework focused on pertinent literature identified on Web of Science, Scopus and Google Scholar; on AI technologies in the construction sector with focus on the South African construction sector. Findings indicated a lack of literature limited to the South African construction sector which signified the importance of the research study in fulfilling the existent knowledge gap.

Figure 4 below indicates the PRISMA flow chart used to explain the manner in which data was collated, screened and analyzed. Through this flow-chart the researchers were focusing on the key themes, key-words and research studies conducted over the past decade for relevant research findings.

Data was collected through the use of specific keyword search in databases which included “artificial intelligence”, “benefits”, “construction”, “machine learning”, “robotics”, “automation”, “South Africa”.

Furthermore, only publications written in the English language were considered, published between 2010 and 2024. Research was filtered according to guidelines pertaining to AI in the construction sector, with focus in a South African context. Data was subsequently gathered on the benefits associated with AI.

An examination was conducted to recognize patterns and trends, offering understanding on the influence of AI in the construction industry in South Africa. The researchers identified 483 papers which were all based on AI in South Africa. The research papers that the researchers had were screened, and 5 research papers were duplicated, 40 papers had different information from what the researchers were looking for and 11 papers were showing abstracts only which totaled to 339 papers that were assessed for eligibility.

Moreover, 88 papers were excluded due to having less information. After complete screening, a total of 117 papers were removed from the research study. 222 research papers were included in the systematic review.

Figure 4: PRISMA flow chart

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The study focused on the primary research objective, to highlight the benefits of AI on the South African construction sector. The organized analysis employed in this research follows a meticulous and methodical process for gathering, categorizing, and understanding data obtained from the literature. A bibliometric analysis was conducted to identify trends in research publications, followed by a systematic review conducted via NVivo to report existing patterns in research data. The bibliometric analysis through VOSviewer was utilized to verify the accuracy and significance of the data examined by highlighting the authors who have conducted recent studies regarding AI in construction and the frequency of the keywords indicated in figures 5 and 6 below. The bibliometric analysis of literature provides important insights into the changing environment of research and application. The figures below illustrate a significant growth in AI-related publications in the construction sector, notably after 2016, corresponding with an increased global interest in AI technology. For example, the number of publications increased from 15 in 2016 to 121 in 2022, indicating a rising understanding of AI's ability to handle construction obstacles such as cost overruns, delays, and safety concerns [37][38]. The United States and China have the highest publications, indicating that they are at the forefront of AI research in construction. However, the analysis emphasizes contributions

from many locations throughout the world, indicating a global interest in using AI to enhance the construction sector.

Figure 5: Co-authorship map visualizing links between jointly authored publications

Figure 6: Keyword co-occurrence

The researchers used qualitative methodologies and an interpretivism philosophy to create a framework for evaluating AI implementation benefits in the South African construction sector. A thematic analysis of qualitative data from published articles was used to identify themes and sub-themes. This research provides insights into the views, experiences, and challenges related to AI introduction in the construction industry. The study employed a detailed process, including gathering, coding, and interpreting data with the help of NVivo for the systematic and thematic analyses. Findings indicated in the table below highlight four key benefits which include: improved efficiency; improved quality; increased safety and overall reduced costs.

Table 2: Benefits of AI Adoption in the South African Construction Industry

Objective	Efficiency	Quality	Safety	Costs
Benefits	Artificial Intelligence has significantly improved; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – industrial efficiency – service delivery – sector operations – project management (improving design processes, quality, risk management and optimizing resource management) – real time monitoring – sustainable construction methods 	Artificial Intelligence has the ability to improve quality by; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – producing high-quality goods – automated inspections – automated materials production (negates errors) 	Artificial Intelligence has the ability to improve safety in the construction sector by; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – automation and robotics for high risk construction activities – maintenance 	Artificial Intelligence has the ability to reduce costs by; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – automation and robotics can complete repetitive operations faster – reduce on site labor costs – new skills development – employment

Nvivo Software: Author Scholar

Findings indicate that AI in South African has the potential to revolutionize the construction sector by addressing infrastructure delivery challenges and in improving efficiency, enhancing quality, safety and construction costs within the construction sector through the adoption of automation, robotics, virtual reality and machine learning; with opportunities for improved stakeholder engagement, environmental efforts, multidisciplinary methods, and educational changes that fosters opportunities for growth [38][39][40][41]. These AI applications facilitate computer-aided design, scheduling, costing, construction automation, and robotics applications on-site. The use of AI in South African construction industry is predicted to result in higher efficiency and cost reductions, highlighting the significance of AI in contemporary construction practices and continual progress in AI presents the opportunity for construction methods that are smarter, sustainable, environmentally friendly and more efficient [26][27][42][43][44]. AI technologies, such as machine learning, computer vision, and predictive analytics, have been shown in studies to considerably enhance project results by increasing productivity and lowering costs by improving resource allocation, scheduling, minimizing waste, and simplifying processes. AI adoption not only simplifies operations but also encourages new practices that can lead to more sustainable building processes, which help both the economy

and the environment. The findings show that, while challenges exist, the long-term benefits of AI adoption in the South Africa's construction sector are significant, paving the path for innovation and increased efficiency. These recommendation for AI adoption across the construction sector aims to address the above challenges while enhancing the construction sectors overall efficiency, quality, safety and improved costs [27][42][43][45][46][47][48].

5. CONCLUSION

The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) provides a transformational potential to overcome the South African construction sectors difficulties and increase efficiency, enhance safety, enhance quality and reduce costs. As the construction sector confronts historical inefficiencies such as labour shortages, project delays, and budget overruns, AI appears as THE disruptive answer, by identifying possible risks and allowing for proactive responses. AI adoption also adds to considerable cost savings by improving resource allocation and scheduling, minimizing waste, and simplifying processes (Rojas and Aramvareekul, 2016). Construction sector organizations may optimize workflows, cut costs, and improve decision-making processes by using AI-driven technologies such as predictive analytics, machine learning, and automation (Bock, 2015). Furthermore, AI improves risk management and stakeholder cooperation, which leads to better project outcomes. The wider economy experiences advantages from AI in construction through job creation and skill enhancement. While AI technology may eliminate certain manual jobs, it also creates opportunities for learning and growth in new positions associated with AI upkeep and integration. In South Africa, utilizing AI in the construction industry could lead to job creation in technology fields and promote economic diversification, tackling the ongoing problem of high unemployment rates. Although AI in South Africa is in its infancy compared to developed nations, there is a growing momentum in the construction sector that is aimed at developing AI for societal and economic benefits while ensuring ethical and regulatory standards are maintained [7][32][36]. The economic impact of integrating AI into the South African construction sector on strategic investments in AI infrastructure, research, and development. Consistent support from government and professional stakeholders, incentives for adopting technology, and partnerships between academia and industry; are essential for maximizing the economic advantages of AI in the South African construction sector [32][42][45][49].

In April 2024, the Department of Communications and Digital Technologies (DCDT) released the Draft National Artificial Intelligence (AI) Plan which displays a significant step towards embracing the future of AI. The National AI Plan highlights government's vision for integrating AI into various sectors and promoting innovation. The plan serves as a guide for further development of the legal, governance, and regulatory framework to be used across South Africa. The AI National Plan aims to provide a step-by-step guide for the development of an implementation of AI, seeking to inspire and encouraging individuals and/or organizations to adopt AI. This research study recommends the Council for the Built Environment in consultation with the Construction Industry Development Board to establish a uniform framework for AI implementation across the South African construction sector. The Construction Sector Artificial Intelligence Framework of South Africa (CSAIF), guided by the

National AI Plan should aim to pave the way for innovative sector collaborations and global investments that encourage innovation and economic success [49][50].

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